

Using the FREYA PID Graph to help reproduce scientific research

Instruct-ERIC facilitates access to cutting edge research infrastructure, within the domain of Structural Biology. Through Instruct, researchers can gain access to techniques, services and equipment in order to perform their research.

The operation of some of this equipment is, to say the least, complex, and for any given piece of research output, there are a large number of inputs that contribute to that output. Many of these inputs are critical for someone who wants to reproduce a given piece of research, and we need to make these findable. In addition, by identifying and documenting every step in the process, from proposal to publication, it should be possible to reproduce and optimise these preparation techniques which could also identify commonalities in the process.

Inputs for a given research output may include but are not limited to; the sample (origin, characteristics, purity, descriptors), its preparation (reagents, formulation, modifications), the machine(s) used, the configuration of the machine(s) at the time, one or more areas of interest in multiple frames of multiple terabytes of HD video, the software and software version, algorithm and parameters used to perform any data processing, the researchers involved, and more.

An additional complexity is that some of this information may need to remain in situ, either because it's impractical to move due to the volume of data involved, or because of contractual or ethical confidentiality reasons.

Using the PID Graph (Fenner & Aryani, 2019) would give us the opportunity to construct, on demand, a "research bundle". This would tell any future researcher, in detail, what inputs went in to producing any given research output and where that data resides. This would allow our research infrastructures to conform to FAIR principles, as well as meet any requisite data protection obligations.

How this might be accomplished

The basic concept is as follows.

For any given experimental session, in any given institution, Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) will be minted to describe any relevant assets and data. What is going to be “relevant” is of course highly application specific and may also be affected by issues of budget and practicality.

In the domain of structural biology, things that could be considered “relevant” might, for electron microscopy, include the microscope used, its configuration settings at the time, frames of HD video, samples and sample preparation protocol, processing software versions, etc. For crystallography, this may include the beamline used and its settings, diffraction analysis processes and 3d structures identified. For future utility, it would probably make sense to be as inclusive as practical.

In larger institutions, a lot of this is already stored and identified, and existing access management systems could be extended to facilitate this process. Many research infrastructures already have contractual commitments to observe FAIR principles, and so will already have much of the necessary infrastructure in place.

The process would go something like this:

1. On beginning an experimental session, a PID is minted to identify it. This “experimental session identifier” could also include a description of the session, the team members, the institution visited, etc, but this isn’t necessarily required.
2. The research is performed, and relevant assets have PIDs minted for them that all make reference to / “cite” the “experimental session identifier” PID. This identifies each experimental asset to being “part of” the overall experiment.

For research conducted using multiple experimental sessions, crossing multiple institutions, we simply repeat this process. Again, access management systems could easily be extended to make this easy.

3. Once an output has been produced - a paper has been published relating to this research, a protein placed in a data bank, etc - a link between the one or more “experimental session identifier” PIDs and the output is established. The output is “claimed” and a “research identifier” PID minted.

Who does this is not important, but it should be noted that “research outputs supported by institution” is already a key performance indicator (KPI) for almost all research institutions and funding bodies.

The Experimental session Identifier

The Experimental session identifier is a “stub” on to which we hang all the assets of an experiment on.

Because a “session” could potentially last for many hours or days, containing many thousands of assets, it is recommended that the identifier is created at the start. Because of the immutable nature of PIDs, this necessarily means that assets are *linked to* the session, and not the other way around.

Figure 1 An illustration of how an Experimental Session Identifier may be constructed

In order to provide structure, it may also be desirable to create a hierarchy of assets underneath of the session. For example in electron microscopy, a PID identifying a microscope references a PID identifying the microscope’s settings at the time. This is highly context specific however, and so is out of scope here.

It is also recommended to add reference to the research team and research institution at this point.

The Research Identifier

The research identifier establishes a link between the research paper and the experimental assets. It pulls together the multiple sets of experimental assets, which may cross multiple infrastructures over multiple years, and canonically links it to a published paper, leveraging the `relatedIdentifiers` functionality (Fenner et al, 2016).

The identifier is used to essentially assert the claim that “these set of things went in to producing this output”, and can be done after the fact, by the author themselves or perhaps a funding body.

Figure 2 Example of constructing a research identifier referencing published research

The reason for this being a separate entity is twofold. Firstly, it presents a single dataset for any future researcher as point of reference, and also removes the requirement for the author to reverence every single one of those data sets at time of publication.

Additionally, research is typically published many years after any experiment has been performed. Oftentimes “papers published” is a key KPI for research facilities and funding bodies, and so, tying the Research Identifier (which in turn references them) to the published paper in this way allows for its creation by those highly incentivised to do so.

For now, I am suggesting the record be created as type “Dataset”, however if there is an option to use (or create) a more suitable data type, that would be ideal. Maybe for now, starting titles with “Research Data:” might aid in clarity.

Creating this record and “claiming” the research might be tricky, especially if the researcher has visited multiple research institutions. However, it is expected that for those large projects some sort of Access management system (like ARIA) would be employed, and this would likely perform the “claim” on behalf of the researcher. Indeed, at Instruct, our user community has already requested such functionality to be added to ARIA.

Producing a “research bundle”

To produce a “research bundle” it will be necessary to interrogate the final published output, and using the graph, find the research bundle associated with an item, e.g.

```
work(id: "https://doi.org/10.xxxx") {
  id
  citations (resourceTypeId: "Dataset"){
    nodes{
      id
      type
      titles{
        title
      }
    }
  }
}
```

Then, once identified, interrogate the `relatedIdentifiers` in order to find the referenced sessions. These will be referenced Dataset nodes.

Each of which can be further “unpacked” on demand using a similar method to Freya user story 8 (Fenner, 2020), specifically, for each data set, collect all its parts. E.g.

```
dataset(id: "https://doi.org/10.xxxx") {
  id
  titles {
    title
  }
  parts {
    nodes {
      id
      type
      titles{
        title
      }
    }
  }
}
```


What a tool might look like

To have proper utility, the creation of PIDs, linking of data and subsequent retrieval needs to be encapsulated into one or more tools.

I imagine this tool to consist of three main services.

Experiment session manager

This would mainly be a tool for the research infrastructure and would provide tools / APIs to facilitate the production of the research bundle.

I imagine it would work something like this:

1. A researcher makes a booking on a particular machine either ahead of time by prior arrangement, or via drop in session
2. The researcher walks up to a machine and scans a QR code, and are taken to a website.
3. The researcher logs in using their ORCID and clicks “begin session”
 - a. At this point a PID is minted identifying the experiment session, and associates it with the researcher.
 - b. The system adds to the session the PID identifying the machine they’re using
 - c. The system mints PIDs for the booking, the machine’s configuration at the time, and any other information that can be gathered automatically at this time.
4. As the research is conducted other experimental outputs can be added to the session
5. Since the session is associated with the booking, staff can add additional information (processed data, information on samples etc) after the researcher has finished.

Most EC project reporting requires collection of feedback from both the researcher and the research facility. In Access management systems like ARIA, there is already a convenient workflow in place which could easily be extended to collect the details of the “experimental session”.

The Claiming tool

When a paper has been published, we need to link that paper to the various collections of inputs that fed into its production.

For Instruct and for users of ARIA, this would be as simple as adding the PID of the published article to their proposal. This is a feature often requested by our user community, and would allow us to automatically perform the necessary linking.

For others, we need to go back to the PID graph to help.

I imagine something along the lines of a simple website where:

1. A researcher logs in with their ORCID
2. They enter the PID identifying their paper
3. A search is performed to identify data sets produced by that author and allow them to be added to a bundle. Perhaps this search could be further optimised by excluding those not already “part of” an existing dataset.
4. When finished, the user “confirms” the process, a new bundle is created and a PID minted.

Research bundle viewer

This would be a simple microsite, which would bring all of this together.

It would consist of a landing page containing a search box, into which a visitor could then enter the PID identifying the paper they were interested in.

The site would then interrogate the PID graph and drill down in order to find all the relevant research associated with it.

Works Cited

Fenner et al, 2016. *THOR: Conceptual Model of Persistent Identifier Linking*. [Online]

Available at: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.48705>

Fenner, M., 2020. *FREYA WP2 User Story 8: As a longitudinal study, I want to be able to deduplicate the metrics/impact for our data, so that I can see the impact of our study's data as a whole..* [Online]

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.14454/y785-xs19>

Fenner, M. & Aryani, A., 2019. *Introducing the PID Graph*. [Online]

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5438/jwvf-8a66>